

Modeling Regional Variation in Wheat Production Dynamics Using Trend-Based Forecasting Techniques

Laraib Fatima^{1*}, Amna Jamali², Haider Ali³

¹Department of Statistics, Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, Shaheed Benazirabad, Pakistan

²Department of Education, Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, Shaheed Benazirabad, Pakistan

³ Institute of space science, University of the Punjab Lahore, Pakistan

*Correspondence should be addressed to: laraib.fatima@sbbusba.edu.pk

Abstract

The current study is being carried out to take a close look examining the patterns in yield, production, and area of important crops like wheat from all provinces of Pakistan in detail. The proposed research will involve the determination of the best forecasting models to be used in fundamental crop growing. The time series data were analyzed using six different forecasting models applied to the data between the years 1981 and 2023 and they included: single exponential smoothing model, double exponential smoothing model, exponential growth model, S-curve trend model, linear trend model and quadratic trend model. A thorough assessment by the method of error minimization was done to determine the best model to predict both area and production and this includes the Mean Squared Deviation (MSD), Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD) and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE). Due to the relatively low error estimates, the results of the calculations showed that the Double Exponential Smoothing model was significantly more useful in matching the calibration of area and production of wheat across several provinces. However, the S-curve and quadratic trend models were found to be much better performing in some geographic areas compared to the other models; they were able to describe the local growth trends of the crops. It is projected that the results of this research would significantly contribute to the policymakers in coming up with informed policies to manage agricultural areas, optimizing production, pricing policies, and analysis of consumption trends which are all vital towards the food security of Pakistan.

Keywords: Wheat Production, Time series analysis, Trend Models, Production optimization

JEL Classification: C53, Q11, Q12, Q18, C22

1. Introduction

Agriculture is still a stabilizer of the Pakistani economy, accounting almost 24% of the national GDP and as the primary source of income by over 62% of the rural population Amjad et al. (2014). The industry is also a major source of livelihoods, reduction of poverty and stability of a nation as it employs approximately 44 per cent of the national labour force. The agriculture system in Pakistan is the key to food availability and a healthy nutrition system since it is the primary provider of caloric and protein nutrients. Cropping systems with fruits, vegetables, and nutrient plants also promote environmental sustainability and the quality of diets Azam and Shafique (2017). Having 30.5 million hectares of arable land, which is 47 percent of the land area of Pakistan, and is higher than the global average of 38 percent, a clear prediction of crop area, output, and production has become inevitable in development of effective policy making Azam and Shafique (2017). Strong predictions can help policymakers to predict food-supply needs, establish price schedules, resource distribution, control imports or exports, and maintain market stability. As such, time-series forecasting models have been highly used by researchers to study the trends in agricultural production.

Literature highlights the usefulness of statistical forecasting methods of major crops in Pakistan. As an example, Abid et al. (2014) reported the reduction in the acreage area of wheat in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa in favor of other rabi crops, but per-hectare growth in yield helped boost production. Likewise, by relying on time-series data, the article by Abid et al. (2018) assessed time-series forecasting models of maize production and concluded that quadratic trend model is the most precise based on the MAD, MSD, and MAPE measures. There are other studies that have used various trend based and exponential models as a means of predicting agricultural performance. Abid et al. (2018) revealed that the exponential growth model gave the best predictions of production in potato in Pakistan. These findings were also supported by Tunio et al. (2016); Fatima and Khan (2015) which reported that there is an upward trend in potato production following an exponential growth modeling. Through these studies, it is highlighted that they should choose forecasting models that follow underlying patterns of crops.

In addition to the traditional trend models, with the development of modern computing methods, the horizons of agricultural forecasting have been expanded. To take a few examples, Shahzad et al. (2022); Ashcraft and Karra (2021) used deep reinforcement learning to optimize crop growth and use of resources, which can demonstrate how machine learning can be utilized to overcome the inefficiency in production under climatic and demographic constraints. Moreover, Khan et al. (2024); Abbas et al. (2007) compared ARIMA, exponential smoothing, and Holt-Winters models to predict the price of rice in Pakistan and found that more complicated models tend to achieve higher performance than a simple trend-following model. Shahzad et al. (2022); Iqbal et al. (2001) pointed to the effectiveness of ARIMA and SARIMA in predicting wheat with the necessity to consider the differences in climatic conditions in different regions. Karim et al. (2010) used time-series and growth models to examine changes in sugarcane production and revealed the impact of adjustments in agriculture inputs to the industry on the accuracy of long-term predictions. These findings are reflected in international literature; in their study, ?Abbasi et al. (2015) have observed that the performance of models differs by region because of climate, soil fertility and management practices, and thus, regional variation is important in forecasting studies.

Although there are significant contributions, previous studies of major crops in Pakistan have considered mostly only single commodities, specifically, maize, potato, or rice, and only a few geographic areas. In addition, there are not many studies that have undertaken the systematic comparison of a broad array of forecasting models in all the provinces based on long-term data. Taking into consideration that Pakistan has the most strategic staple crop, which is wheat, and is a significant proportion of the caloric intake and food-security planning, this is of utmost importance; a thorough analysis of both national and provincial forecasting models is in critical demand Khubaib et al. (2021); Aziza (2022); Costamagna et al. (2007)

To fill this gap, this study examines the area, yield and production of wheat in the various Pakistan provinces as a time-series of the 1980-81 to 2023 time series data. These include six forecasting models, including single exponential, double exponential, exponential growth, S-curve trend, linear trend, and quadratic trend, which are compared on the basis of error-minimization criteria (MAD, MSD, and MAPE). In a bid to find out the best forecasting model to be used in predicting the dynamics of wheat accurately, it is important to bring in the regional variation in the patterns of agriculture into the study. The results should enlighten policymakers in creating evidence-based policies in managing resources in agriculture, maximizing production, price models, and long-term food-security.

Objective

- To analyze long-term trends in the cultivation of wheat in Pakistan, production, and yield.
- To determine the overall appropriateness of trend based and smoothing forecasting models in forecasting dynamic production of wheat.
- To investigate regional differences in the patterns of wheat production to make informed agricultural planning and policy making.

2. Methodology

2.1 Study Area and Time Frame

This paper compares the production of wheat in the four provinces in Pakistan namely Punjab, Sindh, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK), and Balochistan and on the national basis. The analysis uses yearly time-series data, which has been in operation since the year 1980 up to 2023 and this allows the evaluation of long-term patterns and variations in the area of wheat planting, production, and yield between regions.

2.2 Data Sources and Variables

The data were extracted from official Government of Pakistan publications, Azam and Shafique (2017); Amjad et al. (2014) including the Agricultural Statistics of Pakistan and the Economic Survey of Pakistan. These sources provided the records of annual wheat cultivation area (in thousand hectares), production (in thousand tonnes), and yield (in kilograms per hectare) of each province and the country in general. There was intensive verification of all the information to make it consistent and complete. Minor values gaps were solved by interpolating between them hence maintaining

continuity in the series over time. The three main variables of interest included area of wheat, production of wheat, and derived wheat yield per hectare.

2.3 Forecasting Models

The dynamics of wheat production were analyzed and predicted using six time-series forecasting models. These models cover a wide range of trend behaviours and forms of functions. The models of forecasting are provided below:

2.3.1 Linear Trend Model

The linear trend model provides a basis time series tool for analysis and forecasting systematic changes in variables over time, such as the area under cultivation or the production of major crops. The model estimates the direction of long-term change due to temporal trends by assuming a linear trend exists between time and the variable of interest within sub-populations. This methodology allows analysts, planners, and policymakers to discern patterns beneath the surface of deeply interconnected systems, helping them better guide decisions on crop management, resource allocation, and future production planning. The linear trend model in general functional form can be written as Gujarati (2013):

$$Z_t = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 t + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

This model provides a straightforward yet effective method for detecting long-term growth or decline patterns in agricultural time series.

2.3.2 Quadratic Trend Model

Quadratic trend model is an effective analytic technique for considering the temporal changes and predicting key agricultural indicators like harvested area and crop production. Unlike linear models, it allows for non-linear growth curves as it assumes a parabolic relationship between the dependent variable and time; because of this, it is able to capture periods of acceleration, deceleration, or inflection in developmental trends. This method is especially useful for recognizing the long-term structural change of plantings, yield, and production momentum. By incorporating a second-order polynomial into historical time series data, the model provides agricultural researchers and policymakers with an insight into trend patterns, a refined strategic planning of crops and resource allocation, and efficient producing of policy aimed at building sustainable agriculture. The quadratic trend model is formally expressed as Gujarati (2013):

$$Z_t = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 t + \gamma_2 t^2 + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

2.3.3 Exponential Growth Model

Exponential growth model is a popular method for analysis and forecasting of the changes over time in variables like land area, productivity of plants, etc. This model assumes that the derivative of a variable is proportional to its value and leads to exponential growth or decay. It is especially powerful in detecting the trends to how patterns become increasingly intense with time, which is often seen in ecological and agricultural processes. These mathematical relationships make it possible for agricultural researchers and policymakers to estimate future trends, plan the allocation of resources, optimal crop production strategies, and effective policies for agriculture under a rapidly changing environment by fitting an exponential curve regression with historical data. This exponential growth model can be represented mathematically as Gujarati (2013):

$$Z_t = \gamma_0 e^{\gamma_1 t} \quad (3)$$

When $\gamma_1 > 0$, the model describes exponential growth; when $\gamma_1 < 0$, it represents exponential decay. Estimation is typically performed via nonlinear least squares after logarithmic transformation to linearize the relationship:

2.3.4 S-Curve Model (Pearl–Reed Logistic Trend Model)

The S-curve model, known as the Pearl–Reed logistic trend model, serves as an advanced forecasting method to study and forecast agricultural data including cultivated land size, crop output, and yield optimization. The logistic model describes bounded growth through its S-shaped pattern, which

starts with slow adoption followed by fast exponential expansion before reaching its upper limit. The logistic model shows excellent performance for modeling agro-economic systems because it follows an S-shaped pattern that represents growth restrictions from biological, technological, and environmental factors. The model applies to three types of agricultural systems, which include new farming techniques spread, restricted land resources, and maximum crop yields under particular environmental and technological conditions. The Pearl-Reed logistic model is mathematically represented as Gujarati (2013):

$$Z_t = \frac{\gamma_0}{1 + \gamma_1 e^{-\gamma_2 t}} \quad (4)$$

2.3.5 Single Exponential Smoothing Model:

The Single Exponential Smoothing Model serves as a time series forecasting method to study and predict upcoming changes in crop area and production data. The model uses exponential weight distribution to past data points, which increases recent observation importance while reducing older observation influence. The Single Exponential Smoothing Model performs best when data lacks both trend and seasonal patterns. The Single Exponential Smoothing Model enables agricultural researchers and policymakers to create precise short-term predictions, which help them plan crop production, distribute resources, and respond to current agricultural conditions. This model can be expressed through the equation Gujarati (2013):

Forecasting Equation

$$\hat{Z}_{t+1} = \alpha Z_t + (1 - \alpha)\hat{Z}_t \quad (5)$$

Smoothing Equation

$$\hat{Z}_t = \alpha Z_t + (1 - \alpha)\hat{Z}_{t-1} \quad (6)$$

2.3.6 Double Exponential Smoothing Model:

The Double Exponential Smoothing (DES) model, also known as Holt's linear trend method, extends simple exponential smoothing to account for trends in time-series data. Let $S'(t)$ denote the single-smoothed series obtained by applying simple exponential smoothing to the original series $Y(t)$. The single smoothing equation is defined as Gujarati (2013):

$$S'(t) = \alpha Y(t) + (1 - \alpha)S'(t - 1) \quad (7)$$

To capture the underlying trend, a second smoothing process is applied to $S'(t)$. Let $S''(t)$ represent the double-smoothed series, calculated as:

$$S''(t) = \alpha S'(t) + (1 - \alpha)S''(t - 1) \quad (8)$$

Using these two smoothed series, the one-period-ahead forecast $\hat{Y}(t + 1)$ is obtained from:

$$\hat{Y}(t + 1) = a(t) + b(t) \quad (9)$$

2.4 Accuracy Measurements

The three-accuracy metrics, often known as forecasting mistakes, served as the foundation for the forecasting methodologies' dependability. Among these metrics are Mean Squared Deviation (MSD), Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE). These three predicting mistakes or accuracy metrics were used to choose the best-fitting model. The best-fitting model for forecasting is the one with the smallest error term values (Karim et al., 2010). Forecasting error, also referred to as an accuracy measure, is the discrepancy between the actual and fitted value for time series data. Each one will be discussed as follows:

2.4.1 Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE)

MAPE is a relative measure that expresses the error in terms of percentage and is calculated as follows:

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum \left| \frac{e_t}{Z_t} \right|$$

Where: $e_t = Y_t - \hat{Y}_t$ is the deviation between observed and forecast values at time t , $Z_t = Y_t$ is the observed value at time t , and n is the total number of observations.

2.4.2 Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD)

MAD expresses accuracy in terms of the same units as the data by calculating the average of the unknown mistakes. It is an accuracy metric that is more sensitive. The average gap between each data item and the mean is of more concern. MAD is defined as:

$$\text{MAD} = \frac{1}{n} \sum |e_t|$$

Where: $e_t = Y_t - \hat{Y}_t$ is the deviation between observed and forecast values at time t and n is the total number of observations.

2.4.3 Mean Squared Deviation (MSD)

Another metric for assessing a model's forecasting performance is MSD. Because errors are squared before being added, it assigns greater weight to large errors than to minor ones.

$$\text{MSD} = \frac{1}{n} \sum e_t^2$$

Where: $e_t = Y_t - \hat{Y}_t$ is the deviation between observed and forecast values at time t and n is the total number of observations.

3. Results and Discussion

Punjab Wheat Analysis

The table 1 gives the 5-year average for area, production, and yield of wheat in Punjab for the period 1981-2023. In the table, it is shown that there were changes during different periods of 5 years in the area, production, and yield measured in kg per hectare of wheat.

Table 1: Trend in Area, Production and Yield of wheat in Punjab (5-Years Average)

Years	Area ('000 hectares)	Production ('000 tons)	Yield (kg/hectare)
1981-85	5241.8	8653.3	1649.2
1986-90	5577.2	9817.4	1759.1
1991-95	5855.2	11919.1	2035.2
1996-00	6029.0	14257.8	2360.6
2001-05	6263.4	15947.9	2544.3
2006-10	6655.1	17768.0	2669.1
2011-15	6758.1	18974.7	2807.5
2016-20	6595.4	19664.8	2943.5
2021-23*	6520.4	20628.5	3164.4

Accompanying this table would likely be a graph showing trends in the increase or decrease of area, production, and yield over time. It would become very easy to spot how dramatically wheat production and yield have improved, especially in the rise of yield per hectare. Table 2 shows the diagnostic measures that will help in choosing a suitable model for forecasting wheat crop area and production in Punjab. Based on these criteria, the Quadratic Trend model was selected for area, MAPE is 2.0, MAD is 123.5, and MSD is 24660.9, while for production s was selected, MAPE is 5, MAD is 638, and MSD is 622820.

Table 3 presents the forecasts for wheat crop area and production in Punjab. The forecast for area in 2023-24 is 6690.43. The forecast for production in 2023-24 is 6840.98. The forecast for area in 2024-25 is 6687.04. The forecast for production in 2024-25 is 6859.62. The forecast for area in 2025-26 is 6681.67. The forecast for production in 2025-26 is 6877.57.

This figure 1 is the graphical output for the quadratic trend model analysis for wheat crops in Punjab. The blue line shows the actual area of wheat crops, the red line shows the fitted values, and the green line indicates the forecasted values. The model fits quite well in the data, with a rather low MAPE and MAD. It foresees the area of wheat crops to further increase in the near future Khan (2019); ?.

The figure 1 is based on a trend analysis of wheat crop production in the geography of Punjab. The real data is plotted using the blue dots, and the fitted S-Curve trend model is represented in the form of red squares. The future predictions are plotted as green dots. On the right-hand, the table shows the curve parameters: intercept, asymptote, and asymmetric rate and the accuracy measures given by MAPE, MAD, and MSD.

Table 2: Diagnostic procedures for selecting an appropriate model for production and location of wheat crop in Punjab

Forecasting Model	MAPE		MAD		MSD	
	Area	Production	Area	Production	Area	Production
Linear Trend	2.5	5	158.0	737	41460.5	858013
Quadratic Trend	2.0	5	123.5	674	24660.9	680761
Exponential Growth	2.6	7	166.3	1011	46517.9	1709174
S Curve	2.0	5	129.1	638	28046.5	622820
Single Exponential	2.2	6	134.2	888	27775.4	1272812
Double Exponential	2.3	6	140.7	784	30789.1	998928

Table 3: Quadratic trend for area and S-curve trend for production forecasting model of wheat crop in Punjab

Forecast Year	Forecasted Area ('000 ha)	Forecasted Production ('000 ton)
2023-24	6690.43	6840.98
2024-25	6687.04	6859.62
2025-26	6681.67	6877.57

Figure 1: Trend model analysis for wheat crops in Punjab

Sindh Wheat Analysis

This table 4 gives 5-year average data concerning wheat areas, production, and yields in Sindh from 1981-2023. The data were given for the area in '000 hectares, production in '000 tones, and yield in kg per hectare.

Table 4: Trend in Area and Production of wheat in Sindh (5-Years Average)

Years	Area ('000 hectares)	Production ('000 tons)	Yield (Yield per hectare in kg)
1981-85	1021.3	2085.0	2021.8
1986-90	1040.9	2231.6	2144.2
1991-95	1087.4	2312.8	2128.1
1996-00	1061.1	2601.2	2466.4
2001-05	887.5	2328.3	2618.0
2006-10	1048.0	3670.4	3497.3
2011-15	1098.1	3773.8	3438.4
2016-20	1129.7	3844.0	3344.4
2021-23*	1210.0	3748.5	3096.0

The graph would give the trends of the data, showing where wheat production and yield have varied over the years. It would indicate the notable periods of increase and decrease, more especially the peak yields that have been seen at certain times Noonari et al. (2015); Shah et al. (2021)

Table 5 shows the diagnostic measures that will help in choosing a suitable model for forecasting wheat crop area and production in Sindh. Based on these criteria, the double exponential smoothing model was selected for area and production, MAPE is 3.58, MAD is 35.76, and MSD is 4197.39, and for production MAPE is 6.8, MAD is 194.4, and MSD is 75661.5

The forecasts for wheat crop area and production by double exponential models for the forecast years 2023-24, 2024-25 and 2025-26 have been worked out, and the predicted area and production comes out to be 1240.45 and 3950.35 respectively in 2023-24, and 1250.09 and 4001.98 respectively in 2024-25, 1259.74 and 4053.60 respectively in 2025-26. The models give fairly reliable estimates, which are of vital importance in agricultural planning and resource allocation in Sindh.

Figure 2: Area and Production trend in Sindh

Table 5: Diagnostic procedures for choosing suitable model for wheat crop area and production in Sindh

Forecasting Model	MAPE		MAD		MSD	
	Area	Production	Area	Production	Area	Production
Linear Trend	6.71	10	66.96	259	7670.30	121353
Quadratic Trend	6.25	9	63.12	249	6195.75	112167
Exponential Growth	6.76	9	67.78	254	7657.82	115053
Single Exponential	3.59	7.3	36.17	212.4	4050.61	73746.7
Double Exponential	3.58	6.8	35.76	194.4	4197.39	75661.5

Table 6: Double exponential smoothing for area and production forecasting model of wheat crop in Sindh

Forecast Year	Area ('000 ha)			Production ('000 ton)		
	Lower Limit	Forecast	Upper Limit	Lower Limit	Forecast	Upper Limit
2023-24	1152.85	1240.45	1328.05	3474.18	3950.35	4426.53
2024-25	1129.64	1250.09	1370.54	3347.94	4001.98	4656.02
2025-26	1104.15	1259.74	1415.32	3209.24	4053.60	4897.96

In table 6 wheat area that is forecasted shows an increasing trend, though the actual area has ups and downs. All these accuracy measures indicate a reasonably good fit for the model.

Figure 3: Trend model analysis for wheat crops in Sindh

This graph 3 indicates wheat crop production in Sindh. The blue line represents the actual production, while the red represents the fits, the green represents the forecasts, and the purple line represents the 95% prediction interval. It is concluded from the graph that the production increased until 2009, but remained stable with a slight decrease.

KPK Wheat Analysis

The table 7 presents the 5-year average data for the area, production, and yield of wheat in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa from 1981-2023. The measurement is in terms of '000 hectares for the area, '000 tons for production, and kg per hectare for yield.

Table 7: Trend in Area, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa's wheat yield and production (5-Year Average)

Years	Area ('000' hectares)	Production ('000' tones)	Yield (kg per hectare)
1981–85	783.9	907.3	1149.2
1986–90	809.2	1022.6	1261.4
1991–95	850.3	1172.7	1379.0
1996–00	843.1	1094.8	1291.2
2001–05	738.1	1034.4	1402.4
2006–10	750.8	1149.0	1530.6
2011–15	747.7	1282.3	1713.3
2016–20	743.1	1303.3	1730.0
2021–23*	765.5	1421.0	1856.1

Table 8 shows the diagnostic measures that will help in choosing a suitable model for forecasting wheat crop production and area in Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa. Based on these criteria, the single exponential smoothing model was selected for area and production, MAPE is 4.17, MAD is 32.96 and MSD is 1665.99, and for production MAPE is 7.5, MAD is 82.4, and MSD is 12196.7.

Table 8: Diagnostic measures for choosing suitable model for wheat crop area and production in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa

Forecasting Model	MAPE (Area)	MAPE (Production)	MAD (Area)	MAD (Production)	MSD (Area)	MSD (Production)
Linear Trend	3.061	8.5	24.192	91.2	955.075	13422.6
Quadratic Trend	3.20	8.3	25.00	88.6	1177.24	13224.9
Exponential Growth	4.13	8.3	32.78	90.4	1704.07	13318.1
S Curve	4.14	8.4	32.76	91.5	1696.30	14427.1
Single Exponential	4.17	7.5	32.96	82.4	1665.99	12196.7
Double Exponential	4.21	8.2	33.15	88.0	1624.93	14022.6

The forecasts for wheat crop area and production by single exponential models for the forecast years 2023-24, 2024-25 and 2025-26 have presented in 9, and the predicted area and production comes out to be 766.154 and 1431.89 respectively in 2023-24, and 766.154 and 1431.89 respectively in 2024-25, 766.154 and 1431.89 respectively in 2025-26.

Table 9: Single exponential method for area and production forecasting model for wheat crop in Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa

Forecast Year	Area Lower Limit	Area Forecast	Area Upper Limit	Production Lower Limit	Production Forecast	Production Upper Limit
2023-24	706.886	766.154	825.423	1230.07	1431.89	1633.70
2024-25	706.886	766.154	825.423	1230.07	1431.89	1633.70
2025-26	706.886	766.154	825.423	1230.07	1431.89	1633.70

The graph 4(a) shows the trends in these variables over time and, hence, wheat yield trends and changes in cultivated area. This would give an indication of those periods when productivity gains were very high. This plot 4(b) showing the area of wheat planted in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, the actual values, fitted values, forecasts and 95% prediction intervals, and the smoothing constant used in the model. In plots 4(c) single exponential method smoothing for KPK. On the x-axis is the time, while on the y-axis is the production in 000s of per hec. With the blue line representing actual production, the red representing the fitted, and the green representing the forecasted production. From the plot, it can be shown that the single exponential method smoothing gives a good fit to the data. Accuracy measures are presented in the box to the right.

Baluchistan Wheat Analysis

The table 10 shows 5-year average data with respect to wheat's area, production, and yield in the Baluchistan region from 1981-2023. The table expresses the areas in thousands of hectares, production in thousands of tons, and yield in kg per hectare.

Table 11 shows the diagnostic measures that helps in choosing a suitable model for forecasting wheat crop area and production in Baluchistan. Based on these criteria, the exponential growth curve trend model was selected for area and double exponential smoothing model for production,

Figure 4: Trend model analysis for wheat crops in KPK

Table 10: Trend in Area and Production of Wheat in Baluchistan (5-Year Average)

Years	Area ('000 hectares)	Production ('000 tonnes)	Yield (kg per hectare)
1981–85	262.3	407.1	1551.2
1986–90	272.7	526.6	1945.1
1991–95	358.6	788.2	2202.1
1996–00	334.3	707.0	2113.6
2001–05	333.7	649.2	1948.3
2006–10	387.3	774.8	1994.1
2011–15	383.8	845.9	2203.2
2016–20	412.8	951.8	2311.7
2021–23*	509.2	1386.7	2718.5

MAPE is 8.38, MAD is 28.16 and MSD is 1515.81, and for production MAPE is 12.2, MAD is 83.3, and MSD is 14272.5.

Table 11: Diagnostic measures for choosing suitable model for wheat crop area and production in Baluchistan

Forecasting Model	MAPE		MAD		MSD	
	Area	Production	Area	Production	Area	Production
Linear Trend	8.64	15.3	29.04	111.3	1518.19	20615.7
Quadratic Trend	8.53	16.1	28.59	114.0	1512.97	20059.6
Exponential Growth	8.38	15.3	28.16	110.7	1515.81	19904.5
S Curve	8.77	14.4	30.02	108.8	1652.64	23971.2
Single Exponential	9.68	12.3	32.21	87.5	1749.60	14510.5
Double Exponential	9.69	12.2	31.16	83.3	1675.41	14272.5

In table 12 double exponential smoothing model for production, the forecasted years of 2023-24, 2024-25, and 2025-26. In these models, the predicted area and production turn out to be 459.613 and 1519.07, respectively, in 2023-24, 465.829 and 1567.03, respectively, in 2024-25, and 472.12 and 472.12, respectively, in 2025-26.

Table 12: Growth curve for area and double exponential for production of wheat crop in Baluchistan

Forecast Year	Forecasted Area	Forecasted Production	Lower	Upper
2023-24	459.613	1519.07	1314.93	1723.21
2024-25	465.829	1567.03	1290.08	1843.99
2025-26	472.12	1615.00	1259.94	1970.05

Pakistan Wheat Analysis

This table13 gives the 5-year average values for wheat area, production, and yield of whole Pakistan from 1981-2023. It contains areas in yield in kilograms per hectare, production in thousand tons, and thousand hectares.

In table 14 diagnostic measures helps in choosing a suitable model for forecasting wheat crop area and production in Pakistan Based on these criteria, the Quadratic trend model was selected for the area and the S-curve trend model for production. The MAPE is 2.0, MAD is 169.5, and MSD is 169.5 for the area, and for production, MAPE is 4, MAD is 797, and MSD is 951038.

Table 13: Trend in Area and Production of Wheat in Pakistan (5-Years Average)

Years	Area ('000' hectares)	Production ('000' tones)	Yield (kg/ha)
1981–85	7309.3	12052.8	1643.6
1986–90	7700.0	13598.1	1764.8
1991–95	8151.6	16192.7	1986.1
1996–00	8267.5	18660.9	2255.4
2001–05	8222.7	19959.7	2425.5
2006–10	8841.3	23362.2	2641.9
2011–15	8987.7	24876.7	2767.5
2016–20	8881.0	25763.9	2899.7
2021–23*	9005.1	27184.6	3018.6

Table 14: Diagnostic procedures for selecting an appropriate model for Pakistan's wheat crop area and production

Forecasting Model	MAPE		MAD		MSD	
	Area	Production	Area	Production	Area	Production
Linear Trend	2.2	4	187.6	821	187.6	1061250
Quadratic Trend	2.0	4	169.5	835	169.5	978581
Exponential Growth	2.3	5	195.0	1039	195.0	1873704
S Curve	2.1	4	180.1	797	180.1	951038
Single Exponential	2.2	6	185.7	1110	185.7	1849145
Double Exponential	2.3	6	191.1	1020	191.1	1474101

In table 15 quadratic trend model used to forecasts of wheat crop area and S-curve trend model for production, the forecasted years of 2023-24, 2024-25, and 2025-26. In these models, the predicted area and production turn out to be 9065.84 and 27970.9, respectively, in 2023-24, 9078.36 and 28262.2, respectively, in 2024-25, and 9089.39 and 28544.7, respectively, in 2025-26. The estimates from the models are quite reliable and hence very important for agricultural planning and resource allocation in Pakistan.

Table 15: Quadratic trend for area and S-curve trend for production forecasting for wheat crop in Pakistan

Forecast Year	Forecasted Area ('000 hac)	Forecasted Production ('000 ton)
2023–24	9065.84	27970.9
2024–25	9078.36	28262.2
2025–26	9089.39	28544.7

This graph shows a trend analysis plot for the wheat crop area of Pakistan. In the graph, the actual data values are shown by the blue line, the fitted values by the red line, and the green line refers to the forecasted values. The model fits well, reflected in the low MAPE, MAD, and MSD. The plots indicate that the wheat crop area has been increasing in Pakistan.

Figure 5: Trend model analysis for wheat crops in Pakistan

4. Conclusion

In this work, time series modeling from 1981 to 2023 is used, proving that there are significant trends in wheat areas and production across the provinces of Punjab, Sindh, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa,

and Baluchistan. Punjab's wheat production and area have somewhat increased, according to the Quadratic Trend model's results; thus, the province's prospects appear promising in this respect. Conversely, Sindh's wheat production and area show a steady upward trend predicted by the Double Exponential Smoothing model, indicating stability with little increase. The Single Exponential Smoothing model predicts that Khyber Pakhtunkhwa will continue to trend positively with only slight variations. In contrast, the Double Exponential Smoothing model predicts a minor rise in wheat production with bigger forecast errors, whereas the Exponential Growth model anticipates changes in wheat areas in Baluchistan.

These results also highlight the necessity of focused interventions and the use of more sophisticated farming practices to counteract any downturns and guarantee ongoing advancements in wheat output. For efficient strategic planning and policy making, the quadratic trend and other perfect forecasting models, like exponential smoothing, can be quite useful. To meet the food security needs of Pakistan's rapidly expanding population, well-funded research projects and robust government backing will be required to secure and enhance rice crop yields.

Author Contributions

All authors contributed equally to the conception, design, analysis, and writing of this study. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

Funding

This research received no external funding.

Data Availability Statement

The data set is available and shared in Manuscript and defined in methodology section.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Article History:

Received: August 14, 2025

Revised: October 22, 2025

Accepted: October 30, 2025

Published: November 15, 2025

References

- Abbas, M., Sheikh, A. D., Shahbaz, M., and Afzaal, A. (2007). Food security through wheat productivity in Pakistan. *Sarhad Journal of Agriculture*, 23(4):1239.
- Abbasi, S. S., Tahir, A., Raza, I., and Abid, S. (2015). Trend analysis and forecasting of wheat and rice prices in Pakistan. *Pakistan J. Agric*, 28(3):310–317.
- Abid, S., Jamal, N., Anwar, M. Z., and Zahid, S. (2018). Exponential growth model for forecasting of area and production of potato crop in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Agricultural Research*, 31(1):24–28.
- Abid, S., Raza, I., Khalil, A., Masood, M. A., Saqib, A., Khan, M. N., and Masood, M. A. (2014). Trend analysis and forecasting of maize area and production in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *European Academic Research*, II(4):4653–4664.
- Amjad, N., Abbas, S. G., Ahmad, T., and Ali, I. (2014). Agricultural mechanization statistical database development in Pakistan.
- Ashcraft, C. and Karra, K. (2021). Machine learning aided crop yield optimization. In *Association for the Advancement of Artificial Intelligence*, pages 1–4.
- Azam, A. and Shafique, M. (2017). Agriculture in Pakistan and its impact on economy. *A Review. Inter. J. Adv. Sci. Technol*, 103:47–60.

- Aziza, J. N. (2022). Perbandingan metode moving average, single exponential smoothing, dan double exponential smoothing pada peramalan permintaan tabung gas lpg pt petrogas prima services. *Jurnal Teknologi Dan Manajemen Industri Terapan*, 1(1):35–41.
- Costamagna, A. C., Van Der Werf, W., Bianchi, F. J. J. A., and Landis, D. A. (2007). An exponential growth model with decreasing r captures bottom-up effects on the population growth of *aphis glycines matsumura* (hemiptera: Aphididae) a. *Agricultural and Forest Entomology*, pages 1–9.
- Fatima, H. and Khan, M. A. (2015). Influence of wheat varieties on technical efficiency and production of wheat crop in pakistan (in selected area of punjab). *Sarhad Journal of Agriculture*, 31(2).
- Gujarati, D. N. (2013). *Basic Econometrics*. United States Military Academy, California.
- Iqbal, M., Khan, M. A., Ahmad, M., and Ahmad, B. (2001). Determinants of higher wheat productivity in irrigated pakistan [with comments]. *The Pakistan Development Review*, pages 753–766.
- Karim, R. M., Awal, Abdul, M., and Akter, M. (2010). Forecasting of wheat production in bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Agricultural Research*, 35:17–28.
- Khan, M. A. (2019). *Drought assessment of Pakistan and its impact on its agricultural production*. PhD thesis, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign.
- Khan, M. A., Masood, S., and Nasir, A. (2024). Green revolution in khyber pakhtunkhwa (a comparative study with punjab). *Pakistan Research Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(4).
- Khubaib, N., Asad, S. A., Khalil, T., Baig, A., Atif, S., Umar, M., and Baig, S. (2021). Predicting areas suitable for wheat and maize cultivation under future climate change scenarios in pakistan. *Climate Research*, 83:15–25.
- Noonari, S., Memon, M. I. N., Malook, M., Memon, Z., Jamali, R. H., Pathan, A., and Pathan22, M. (2015). Estimating productivity gap and contribution of wheat production in sindh pakistan. *Journal of Resources Development and Management*, 10:104–116.
- Shah, S. M., Liu, G., Yang, Q., Casazza, M., Agostinho, F., and Giannetti, B. F. (2021). Sustainability assessment of agriculture production systems in pakistan: A provincial-scale energy-based evaluation. *Ecological Modelling*, 455:109654.
- Shahzad, A., Hamid, A., Hussain, A., Rashid, M., Khan, M., and Hussain, Z. (2022). Current situation and future prospects of wheat production in pakistan. *Journal of Life and Social Sciences*, 2022(1):5–5.
- Tunio, A., Magsi, H., and Solangi, M. A. (2016). Analyses of growth trends and production forecast of cash crops in pakistan. *International Journal of Agronomy and Agricultural Research (IJAAR)*, 9(1):158–164.